

4. Regenerated plantlets showing rooting on MS medium containing 1.0 mg IBA L⁻¹.

containing 1.0 mg IBA L⁻¹ (Fig. 4) and were transferred to pots.

Results indicated the usefulness of L-tryptophan and activated charcoal in increasing regeneration of green plants from long-term callus cultures of indica rice. ■

Grain quality

Modeling water uptake and degree of polish of milled rice

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This study was undertaken to model the process of water uptake behavior during cooking and to correlate water uptake with degree of polish for two varieties (coarse Jaya and scented fine Basmati) commonly grown in the western part of Uttar Pradesh, India. Rough rice samples were collected from a farmer's field just after harvest, cleaned, and shade-dried up to milling moisture content (14% dry basis). These were then shelled and polished in a

Satake rice sheller and polisher. Milling / polish time varied from 0 s to 60 s to control the degree of bran removal (degree of polish) with an increment of 15 s. The degree of polish of milled samples ranged from 2.7% to 8.4% for Jaya and 2.9% to 8.5% for Basmati at 15 s and 60 s, respectively.

The 1,000-kernel weight of Jaya (28.6 g) was higher than that of Basmati (24.5 g). The length and width-thickness ratio of Jaya were 8.67 mm and 3.04 mm, respectively, and those of Basmati were 11.09 mm and 5.13 mm. The angle of repose of Basmati (32°) was wider than Jaya's (24.8°). Bulk and true density were determined by measuring the weight of known volumes of samples and by the method of relative density, respectively. Porosity, the index of void space in the bulk, was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Porosity} = \frac{(\text{True density} - \text{bulk density})}{\text{True density}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Table 1 shows the bulk density, true density, and porosity of the two rice varieties.

Table 1. Physical and gravimetric properties of Jaya and Basmati rice.

Property	Jaya	Basmati
Size (mm)		
Length	8.7	11.1
Width	2.8	2.0
Thickness	2.0	1.8
1,000-kernel weight (g)	28.6	24.5
Bulk density (g cc ⁻¹)	0.6	0.5
True density (g cc ⁻¹)	1.3	1.0
Porosity (%)	51.2	51.4
Angle of repose(°)	24.8	32.6

Table 2. Degree of polish, head yield, and water uptake of Jaya and Basmati rice varieties.

Time of milling (s)	Jaya			Basmati		
	D _p ^a	H _y	W _{up}	D _p	H _y	W _{up}
0	0	89.0	–	0	85.0	–
15	2.7	64.3	355	2.9	65.1	352
30	4.6	61.9	357	4.9	63.9	362
45	6.7	58.1	362	6.4	63.1	371
60	8.4	57.2	368	8.5	63.0	384

^aD_p = degree of polish (% on brown rice basis), H_y = head yield (%), and W_{up} = water uptake (g).

Water uptake and kernel elongation after cooking were also determined (Table 2). Kernel elongation was 35% more in Basmati than in Jaya for 6% degree of polish. A similar observation was recorded for different samples of milled rice. Water uptake was found to be more for the same degree of polish for Basmati than for Jaya. Water uptake behavior for Jaya and Basmati can be described by the following equation:

$$W_{\text{up}} = A \times e^{B D_p} \quad (2)$$

where A = 1.71 and B = 0.91.

This mathematical expression describes the kinetics of water uptake (mL) and its relation with degree of polish (%) satisfactorily under obtainable conditions. The correlation coefficient and standard error of estimate for the above equation were 0.987 and 0.089, respectively. ■

Breeding of Gan wan nuo 5, a new high-quality glutinous indica variety

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Gan wan nuo 5, released in 1993 by the Jiangxi Provincial Seed Board, is a new glutinous indica rice variety with high quality. It was derived from the cross MY82166/Ma ba xian nuo. MY82166 is an indica rice with high resistance to blast, whereas Ma ba xian nuo is an aromatic glutinous indica variety. Gan wan nuo 5 is suitable for later season planting in the double-cropped area of southern China and single-cropped area of central China. Yield of this variety averaged 6.8 t ha⁻¹ in double-cropped areas; it was 7.5 t ha⁻¹ in single-cropped areas. This yield was 7% more than that of Jing Nuo 6, a glutinous check, and nearly the same as that of Shan you 63, a check hybrid. Because of its high quality and other good traits (see table), the award-winning Gan wan nuo 5 is replacing Jing Nuo 6 in many areas.

Major traits of Gan wan nuo 5, Rice Research Institute of China, 1992.

Trait	Value
Brown rice (%)	79.7
Milled rice recovery (%)	69.7
Head rice (%)	58.2
Kernel length(mm)	5.5
L-W ratio	2.2
Alkali spreading value	6
Gel consistency (mm)	100
Amylose content (%)	1.6
Protein content of head rice (%)	8.0

Gan wan nuo 5 has a strong, 120-cm-long stem. It has a growth duration of 135-140 d in single-cropped areas. The variety has high yield potential with good irrigation and good management.

Gan wan nuo 5 has a 1,000-grain weight of 25.3 g, panicle length of 24.9 cm, and 141 filled grains panicle⁻¹. The variety is used for making stuffed dumplings, cakes, and sweet wines.

Gan wan nuo 5 is widely planted and is spreading quickly in southern and central China. A total area of 70,000 ha was devoted to the crop from 1992 to 1998. ■

Pest resistance — diseases

Inheritance of resistance to bacterial leaf blight in differential rice variety Asominori

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Asominori is one of the international differentials used for testing the pathogenicity of the bacterial leaf blight (BLB) pathogen, *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae*. It has been one of the varieties most resistant to BLB in Japan since its release in 1973. Extensive testing under the JIRCAS and YAAS collaborative research project on rice genetic resources between 1994 and 1996 showed that Asominori has stable resistance to BLB in both indica and

japonica rice-growing areas in Yunnan, China. Hence, Asominori is considered a useful source of durable resistance to BLB. We found that Asominori has an allele of the *Xa1* locus on chromosome 4 for BLB resistance, although it has been reported to harbor *Xa17* independent from *Xa1*.

First, we found that Asominori grain showed a positive reaction to phenol solution, even though almost all japonica varieties in Japan have been reported to show negative reactions. The trait was inherited as a monogenic character in F₂ plants between Asominori and varieties Kogyoku and St No. 1, which showed a negative reaction to phenol. No segregant had a negative reaction to phenol in the F₃ seeds of each F₂ plant (n = 240) between Asominori and a near-isogenic line of Taichung 65 with a marker *Ph*, suggesting that Asominori had the *Ph* gene on chromosome 4.

To further test the association between phenol reaction of grains and resistance to BLB, we screened 16 varieties or breeding lines in the pedigree of Asominori. Only Saikai 85 displayed a positive phenol reaction

and resistance to BLB isolates. None of the other 15 varieties/lines (Tadukan, Senbonasahi, Pi No. 2, Saikai 97, Jikkoku, Zensho 26, Benisengoku, Chukyoasahi, Ojo, Saikai 59, Chujo 2, Norin 22, Tozan 38, Shinyamabuki, and Sachikaze) showed either of the two traits.

Second, BLB resistance of the varieties and their hybrids was evaluated by the clipping inoculation method around the heading stage in a rice field. Table 1 shows the reaction of parental varieties, F₁, and F₂ plants. All the F₁ plants were resistant to BLB isolates T7174 (race I), H9153 (race II-2), and H75304 (race V), which were collected in Japan. The segregation ratios in the F₂ populations were 3 (resistant): 1 (susceptible), suggesting that BLB resistance in Asominori was controlled by a single dominant gene. The BLB resistance gene of Asominori and *Ph* was closely linked with a recombination value of 2.4% in the coupling phase; all the segregation ratios were consistent with the genetic model (Table 2). This value was also consistent with the 2.8% recombination between *Ph* and *Xa1* reported earlier

Table 1. Segregation for reaction to BLB isolates in F₂ populations between Asominori, Kogyoku, and St No. 1.

Variety or cross combination	Number of plants for each reaction to T7174, H9153, and H75304 ^a				Goodness of fit to 3:1	
	RRR	RSR	SSS	Total	χ^2	Probability
Asominori	15	0	0	15		
Kogyoku	0	15	0	15		
St No. 1	0	0	15	15		
Asominori/Kogyoku (F ₁)	3	0	0	3		
Asominori/St No.1 (F ₁)	5	0	0	5		
Asominori/Kogyoku (F ₂)	296	94	0	390	0.168	0.6-0.7
Asominori/St No.1 (F ₂)	50	0	24	74	2.180	0.1-0.2
Asominori/St No.1 (F ₂)	265 ^b	0	73 ^b	338	2.087	0.1-0.2

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible, RRR stands for resistant reaction to three BLB isolates used, respectively. ^bInoculated by isolates T7174 and H75304 only.

Table 2. Linkage relationship between BLB resistance and a genetic marker *Ph* in F₂ populations between Asominori, Kogyoku, and St No. 1.

Cross combination (F ₂)	Segregation mode ^a				Recombination value ± SE (%) ^b	Goodness of fit	
	AB	Ab	aB	ab		χ^2	Probability
Asominori/Kogyoku	292	4	5	89	2.37 ± 0.78	0.335	0.9-1.0
Asominori/St No. 1	49	1	1	23	2.48 ± 1.83	2.254	0.5-0.6

^aA = a dominant gene for BLB resistance in Asominori; B = *Ph* gene for phenol reaction. ^bWeighted mean of recombination values is 2.4% in a coupling phase.